

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: Abca10.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of Abca10 as a
9 candidate gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

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